

EC – Horizon 2020

Data management plan required?	Yes - for all projects participating in the ORD project unless researchers opt out of the ORD project. Those researchers that opt out of the ORD project are still encouraged to submit a data management plan.
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	<p><i>Data summary</i> Purpose of the data collection/generation Explain the relation to the objectives of the project Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) Specify the origin of the data State the expected size of the data (if known) Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful</p> <p><i>FAIR data principles</i></p> <p><i>Findable</i> Including provisions for metadata Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers? Outline naming conventions used Outline the approach towards search keyword Outline the approach for clear versioning Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how</p> <p><i>Accessible</i> Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so Specify how the data will be made available Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions</p> <p><i>Interoperable</i> Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</p> <p><i>Reusable</i></p>

	<p>Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible</p> <p>Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed</p> <p>Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why</p> <p>Describe data quality assurance processes</p> <p>Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable.</p> <p><i>Allocation of resources</i></p> <p>Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs</p> <p>Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project</p> <p>Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation</p> <p><i>Data security</i></p> <p>Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.</p> <p><i>Ethical aspects</i></p> <p>To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former</p> <p><i>Other</i></p> <p>Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)</p> <p>What standards will be applied?</p> <p>How will data be exploited &/or shared/made accessible for verification & reuse? If data cannot be made available, why not?</p> <p>How will data be curated & preserved?</p>
Required data repository	No
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	No additional funding is provided for data management activities for those deciding to participate in the pilot.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=enquiries (Online enquiries form)
Comments	DMP should be written after funding has been awarded (within 6 months)

Documents used: H2020 online manual: Data management

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Open access and data management http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

H2020 annotated model grant agreement

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=243

Accessed: July 2018